

ISic0430

I.Sicily inscription 0430

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone (?) ('petra syracusana')

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

Not located

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa (?)

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. dis manibus
2. Evange [lus] [v]ixit · an (nis)
4. VIII
5. Thychicus
6. vixit · an (nis) · VI
7. Thyche
8. mater · fil (iis)
9. piissimis
10. fecit

Apparatus

Text of CIL 10.7150

Translation (en)

To the shades of the underworld. Evangelus lived 9 years. Thychicus lived 6 years. Thyche, their
mother, made this for her most loving sons

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491658

EDCS 21900492

Bibliography

Gualtherus, G. 1624. Siciliæ obiacentium insular. et Bruttiorum antiquæ tabulæ, cum animadversionib. Messanae. At no.96

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7150 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650768>)

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